

UNIVERSITY OF
OREGON

School of Journalism
and Communication

Agora Journalism Center

Gather Final Report

May 2018

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What is Gather?

[Gather](#) is a project and online platform to support a [community of practice](#) (CoP) of community-minded journalists and other [engagement](#) professionals who are innovating new strategies so that the norm of journalism becomes more [engaged](#) and [relational](#). [Click [here](#) for more about Gather's long-term vision for journalism and communities.]

With funding from the John S. and James L. [Knight Foundation](#) and [The Democracy Fund](#), the [Agora Journalism Center](#) at the University of Oregon is working with a Portland-based company, [FMYI](#), to create Gather.

The Gather Mission

The mission of *Gather* is to make journalism more responsive to the public's needs and more inclusive of the public's voices and diversity, by helping journalists, educators, and students who share these values find each other, find information and resources, and find support and mentorship.

The Design Process

Gather is being designed and developed through a [collaborative process](#) that includes:

- A [Project Team](#) of paid staff that manages the project and coordinates and facilitates the collaborative approach.
- An all volunteer [Steering Committee](#), created to build a sense of collective ownership of the platform among people from around the country who have been doing something related to Gather, or who are interested in building the engagement community of practice.
- An [Advisory Committee](#) to give input on specific questions and support specific tasks.
- FMYI, the [Tech Partner](#) that provides the digital framework that Gather is built on.
- The [Agora Journalism Center](#), which serves as the project's institutional foundation.

Developmental evaluation to illuminate and support the creation of a digital platform for engagement journalism

This report is on the first developmental year of the Gather project, during which the [Project Team](#) and the [Steering Committee](#) used a process of [developmental evaluation](#) (DE) to successively and iteratively answer questions about and support the design of the platform.

The Evaluation Questions

1. What are we trying to achieve – what is the “[problem](#)” we are trying to solve?
2. What is our [entry point](#) for addressing that problem; with whom do we propose to address it (i.e., who is the [core community of Gather users](#))?

3. What do we need to do to support that community and the engagement work of its members? (what's the needed "[intervention](#)")?
 - a. How did the leadership evolve as we went?
 - b. What are we hearing during development and early testing and use regarding whether a digital platform would be useful and if so what it should do and have?
 - c. What else we need to do for ongoing maintenance and adaptation?
4. What results ("[outcomes](#)") are we hoping Gather will have, and what results are we seeing in the months after Gather's launch?
5. How does what we have observed and learned so far inform [what's next](#)?

The questions and the the answers that we discovered, and the relationships among them are diagrammed in the [Theory of Change](#) illustration below.

Data

Data we used for the developmental evaluation included:

- Surveys of members of the Community of Practice
- Literature reviews ([this one](#) for example)
- Analysis of engagement-related social media sites (such as the [Experience Engagement Facebook Group](#))
- Formal and informal reflective discussions
- Documentation from our partner [Journalism that Matters](#)' conferences and research projects
- Documentation from steering committee and project team meetings
- *Gather* site [analytics](#)
- Information people share in their *Gather* [invitation requests](#) and profiles

These data, which we collected and continually analyzed throughout the development phase, contributed to our current articulation of all of the components of the [Theory of Change](#).

Focus of this report: The development phase

At the time of the writing of this report, Gather has been launched and in public use for a mere six months (with an earlier two months during the beta launch). Thus, as implied in the questions that guided the evaluation, the report focuses on primarily on the development process. It is too early to be able to observe very much in terms of outcomes, even short-term ones, but some data are starting to come in.

As Gather is used and the CoP evolves, we can add to the findings and begin to fill in the other evaluation focuses related to [short term](#) and [long-term](#) outcomes and [impacts](#).

Gather Theory of Change

[A Theory of Change](#) (ToC) describes the process and reasons why the desired change can be expected to happen. ToCs explain and map the relationship between what a project or innovation does (the “intervention”) and how these activities lead or contribute to the achievement of desired goals (short-term and long-term outcomes) and how the project or innovation contributes to impacting the problem it’s designed to address.

As a technique for understanding and supporting an innovation as it comes into being, DE is part of the innovation process. We, therefore, included the evaluation activities and resulting learnings as part of how we think about Gather’s ToC . The arrows on the left and right sides of the diagram on page 7 below indicate the iterative nature of the project; we learned about all aspects of the ToC as we proceeded and adapted our processes, the platform design, the questions we were asking, and the conceptualization of the problem, intervention and outcomes on the way.

The following section elaborates on the components of the ToC by answering the DE questions.

Developmental Evaluation Questions and Learnings: Summary

(for detailed learnings, click [here](#))

Although the ToC seems declarative regarding how we are defining the problem, intervention, outcome, and impact, in reality, the evaluation questions and learnings helped refine these ideas as we went (hence illustrating the iterative nature of the project in the diagram below).

Developmental Evaluation Questions and Learnings: Detail (Second level content that is linked to from First Level)

Evaluation Question #1:

What are we trying to achieve – what is the “problem” we are trying to solve?

With public trust in institutions – including media organizations – at a [historic low point](#), engagement in [general](#), and [relational](#) engagement in particular, offer a means to begin to restore trust and repair relationships between media organizations and the public. However, engagement-oriented media is still in its infancy, and those engagement practitioners who are invested in supporting thriving communities and trusted media are often isolated.

Since 2015, the [Agora Journalism Center](#) and [Journalism That Matters](#) have been working with a [developmental evaluator](#) to understand of the challenges facing the engagement journalism community. According to 2015 [research report](#), techniques and philosophies behind engagement practices are often fragmented. Engagement practitioners often operate alone or in small isolated groups. Ideas, resources, support, and experiences are currently not easily shared across the engagement CoP. This finding was reinforced at the 2017 [Elevate Engagement](#) gathering, and the need for addressing it articulated in the [Elevate Engagement Manifesto](#).

Gather takes on the challenge by providing [the Gather core community](#) a place to discuss and share experiences, ideas, and resources with one another. These community contributions, in turn, are made easily documented and findable by the platform, allowing any member of the community to access and benefit from content shared by any other member of the community. This gathering of practitioners – from which the name of the platform derives – also provides a support network for those looking to introduce community engagement in their local newsrooms or communities that might otherwise be isolated.

Gather’s Long-Term Impact: Civic Communications Ecosystems

Why do we care about engagement? What larger reason do we have for addressing the challenges facing engagement journalism?

Journalism too often causes harm when it is done “to” people instead of with them, by them, and [as them](#). As a result, communities can feel misrepresented or underrepresented by the news media. Stories that are important to these communities are often mistold, assuming they’re told at all.

“When we are ‘covering communities,’ we need to hear from and reflect people who often go unheard. By cultivating relationships, we reduce the high risk of doing harm to people who are already misunderstood or misrepresented.” ([Elevate Engagement Manifesto](#))

The task is not just to reinvent journalism,

“but rather to reimagine journalism in context of a system of communication that fosters trustworthy relationships, encourages learning, develops the capacity for holistic thinking, and inspires organizational responsibility and accountability” ([JTM Engagement Framework](#)).

Reimagining journalism requires vulnerability and risk. We must “recognize the limitations of our own skill sets and [seek] to enlist the public to serve the public’s needs.” (Elevate Engagement Manifesto). Reporters must put their trust in the public’s knowledge and in the engagement process.

The idea of the civic communications ecosystem represents a communications model where media goes from being one-directional to collaborative.

“To be a thriving, resilient ecosystem, communication needs to go beyond ‘reporting’ what is happening in the ecosystem to providing robust information and inclusive dialogue, fostering collaborative action that achieves community goals.”([ITM Engagement Framework](#)).

Evaluation Question #2:

What is our entry point for addressing the problem; with whom do we propose to address it?

The most important thing that we can do to contribute to healthy civic communications ecosystems is to cultivate a [Communities of Practice for engagement journalism](#). In this way, we can build the capacity of journalists, media organizations, and communities to move toward a day when relational engagement becomes integrated with other traditions, forms and practices of journalism.

Through a [review of the literature](#) on Communities of Practice, we identified the following reasons for creating and supporting a CoP:

- CoPs are effective ways for people to share and pass on skills and learn together, and to adapt to changing circumstances. When they are built around an aspiration for innovation, they can be a powerful mechanism to shift stuck cultures and institutionalized ways of doing things from the ground up.
- CoPs require a kind of relational engagement that is very similar to the kind needed for functional relationships between between journalists and communities.
- In the “digital era,” digital tools for communication and collaboration can effectively support growth and engagement in CoPs.
- CoPs thrive on personal relationships and interactions; technology is not enough. Conversation, deliberation, co-learning, collaboration, and the generation of new ideas are examples of these interactions.

The [Manifesto](#) that came out of the May of 2017 [Elevate Engagement](#) conference articulated the aspiration for a CoP:

“We believe engagement can help us build with the public to provide something useful and valuable that sustains community, rather than trying to sell people content they don’t want ... We recognize that people need experiences, connections and relationships, not just information. We start with curiosity and a desire to be a force for good through our storytelling and communication. We offer our own vulnerability and are willing to step out first into difficult conversations and situations. We are inclusive, bringing diverse stakeholders, partners and communities to the conversation ... As engaged journalists, engagement practitioners, and community members, we can be catalysts in

the path toward healthier communities ... [But] many of us do not have in-person colleagues who understand or even support our efforts. We crave a sense of belonging—that feeling that other people get us, like us, and have our back. We want to feel like we’re part of an intentional community ... Because we feel a burning passion and ethical obligation to bring this work into the world, we need to stay connected in a way that allows all of our voices to matter and offers a clear, practical way to ask for support.” ([Elevate Engagement Manifesto](#))

In response, in October, Gather’s Executive Director [Andrew DeVigal](#) asked:

“How can we motivate more journalists (and journalism students) to put the community at the center of their work, be better listeners, and understand more precisely the needs of the public? Until we can think of the public not just as ‘audiences’ and ‘consumers,’ but also as experts and partners in the communities we aim to serve, we shouldn’t expect to receive the public’s complete trust.” ([The Continuum of Engagement](#)).

Together with the findings of the Elevate Engagement Manifesto, this question helped consolidate a vision of how to grow and nurture this CoP.

Evaluation Question #3:

What do we need to do to support the CoP and the engagement work of its members (the “intervention”)?

The team conducted a series of [surveys](#), group discussions and one-on-one conversations with stakeholders in late 2015, which led to the following conclusions about what we need to do:

- Collaborative leadership: The principle of being [relational](#) guides us toward co-ownership, involvement, and leadership of the project. If we foster collaboration among people who have already been innovating in the engagement space, we will increase the likelihood of support and buy-in.
- Design a digital platform: Providing a platform where people can connect with and learn from each other is the needed step to develop, spread, reinforce and continue to adapt relational engagement journalism. The platform will support relational engagement among members of the CoP.
- Ongoing maintenance and adaptation of the platform in response to the evolving needs of the COP, and other contextual changes, is necessary.

COLLABORATIVE LEADERSHIP

Evaluation Question #3a: How did leadership evolve as we went?

FROM THIS -----> TO THIS	
Original Concept	Adaptation
Fully collaborative group decisions , using consensus or voting if necessary. The original design for the collaborative process was codified in a Charter Document .	Consultative , with leadership emerging in the paid Project Team, and volunteer committee giving input and being informed on decisions and progress. The roles and priorities of the Project Team, the Steering and Advisory Committees, and committee sub-groups evolved over the course of the development phase.

What we learned about adapting leadership

The developmental evaluation helped us understand:

- [What was changing](#) in terms of leadership and roles?
- [What was driving the change](#)?
- What were the [conditions that support ongoing development](#) of the innovation of the process, and what conditions [need to be considered](#) in the act of managing the collaborative process?

DESIGN OF THE DIGITAL PLATFORM

Evaluation Question 3b: What are we hearing during development and early testing and use regarding whether a digital platform would be useful and if so what it should do and have?

The original design of the platform was guided initially by input from the [surveys](#), group discussions, and one-on-one conversations with stakeholders held in 2015. Once the steering committee came on board, they provided valuable stakeholder and user input. In addition, we continued to follow engagement journalism discussions on [social media](#) to identify priorities for content and functionality for the platform.

We learned that the CoP needs *Gather* to provide:

- **Value:** People go to the place that has what they urgently need. Whether through case studies, resources, newsletters, or Lightning Chats, *Gather* needs to provide its members with clear, demonstrable value. Members should know that spending 5 minutes (or 60 minutes) each week in the *Gather* ecosystem will make their work better and/or their lives easier.
- **Community:** Community thrives on personal relationships, shared identity and vision, a culture of sharing and collaboration, and the sense of safety to be “who you are.” In addition to providing explicit value through content and programming, *Gather* must also create opportunities for members to provide and receive value to/from each other. It must become a true community of practice, where personal relationships are forged or strengthened and information is exchanged. Informal connection and information sharing without direct intervention by administrators is needed, as is facilitating the weaving together of the community – it’s not enough to just put content out and let people find it.
- **Consistency:** Value is not always recognized overnight, nor is community forged overnight. It will take time for members to discover *Gather*’s offerings and to develop relationships with its other members. **Therefore, what *Gather* must provide is consistency. Week after week, the Lightning Chats, newsletters, and other content/programming must be compelling, relevant, and timely.** Members should know when and where they can show up to read a new case study, find a new job listing, or bounce around ideas with professional colleagues.
- **Responsive technology:** Technology is only helpful if it responds to and supports what people are saying they need both now and in the future; is easy to navigate and use; supports human relationships; and ideally, is supported by a local, available tech partner.

ONGOING MAINTENANCE AND ADAPTATION

(continuing the developmental evaluation)

Evaluation Question 3c: What else do we need to do?

The first set of adaptations implemented in response to what we learned during the development phase was the addition of [adjunct activities](#) to support active engagement among the CoP (occasional [Medium](#) articles, weekly [Lightning Chats](#) and [Newsletter](#), and the [Topic of the Month](#)).

Following the introduction of adjunct activities, *Gather* ended its alpha development phase and launched in a closed beta format on July 27, 2017, with a public beta following in October 2, 2017. People can now join *Gather* by [requesting an invite](#) to participate in the community.

Since launch, we have learned more about what people are hoping *Gather* can provide them. By randomly sampling social media mentions and a selection of what people wrote about their interest in *Gather* when they filled out invitation requests, we have found that while specific interests are diverse, in general, users and prospective users are looking for features and support that align well with the *Gather* mission. Some common interests include:

- Networking with other practitioners
- Receiving feedback on ongoing projects

- Discussing issues that face the industry
- Having a hub to find (and contribute) industry news and resources
- Finding opportunities for collaboration
- Reading case studies and other examples of related projects in action

Next evaluation steps for ongoing adaptation

As people use *Gather*, we are planning to conduct user surveys and/or interviews to continually learn how to serve the needs of the CoP more effectively, and about how those needs are changing.

Examples of questions we'll ask are:

- How are users using *Gather*, and why are they using it?
- Why are some features not being used?
- What do people wish they could find on it but can't yet? What more/else do they want? Are people getting what they came to *Gather* to get?
- How do they feel about the platform (e.g. is it accessible, searchable, easy-to-use, etc.)? Is it valuable? Do they feel that they can't miss it?
- What is easily done on the platform and how much do people rely on other tools (e.g, email, FB, chat, etc.)

Evaluation Question 4: What are the results?

The following are the intended short-term/medium-term and long-term outcomes for the CoP.

Intended short- and medium-term outcomes

- [Members of the CoP will use *Gather* in alignment with the *Gather* mission](#)
- [Activity in *Gather* will be relational \(or will become more so\)](#)
- [Over time, *Gather* users will represent diverse parts of the civic communications ecosystem](#)

Intended long-term outcomes

The *Gather* project and platform aim to help the [engagement community of practice](#) grow as practitioners of Engaged Journalism that bridges the divide between the ideals and practices of traditional media and emergent principles of [relational](#) engagement. By nurturing a robust and mutually-supportive network of engagement practitioners, *Gather* aims to advance Engaged Journalism so that relational engagement becomes integrated with other traditions, forms and practices of journalism. Thus, relational engagement would no longer be an “add on” but would be baked into the way that journalism is done in newsrooms and other media organizations, civic organizations, and communities, without sacrificing professional objectivity or journalistic independence.

Results so far for short-term outcomes

As the majority of the data for this report was collected less than five months after *Gather*'s public beta launch, we are only just starting to observe results.

To what extent is [Gather being used in alignment with the Gather mission](#) and to what extent is [activity on Gather relational](#)?

In the future, we hope to conduct an in-depth content analysis of activity in Gather to determine whether users are using Gather in alignment with the mission and whether use is primarily relational. At this point, the platform lacks the functionality to conduct this type of analysis. However, this functionality is currently being planned for a future release (see [next steps in evaluation short-term outcomes](#)). Based on Project Team members' anecdotal observations of Gather activity so far, as well as limited sampling of third-party mentions of Gather, it does appear as though Gather is being viewed as a powerful relational tool that aligns well with the Gather mission:

“I would love to find people trying to do engagement projects with the end goal of providing better information and greater access to that information in their own community.” – Carolyn Powers, Program Officer at Internews.

“With recent upheaval in the revenue model for journalism, going straight to the people we seek to serve for guidance and support seems one of the more straightforward paths. What are best practices, potential pitfalls, and strong arguments for engagement and journalism?” – Katie Dahl, researcher and writer at the Internet Archive.

“I'm interested in collaborating with others working in engaged journalism to share resources, so we aren't always 'reinventing' the wheel. I also just want a central space to engage with the latest articles and discussions around engagement.” – Cristina Kim, Engagement Manager at Reveal.

“I so appreciate that 1) we are a community of practice, 2) we are growing, developing, building, and evolving, 3) everyone is welcome to the degree they are able to participate, 4) we're learning by doing, and will iterate.” – jesikah maria ross, Senior Community Engagement Strategist at Capital Public Radio.

To what extent do [Gather users represent diverse parts of the civic communications ecosystem](#)?

[Analytics data as of March 1, 2018](#) showed that there were 1101 active members.

Those users came from 41 states, Washington, D.C and 55 countries on all continents except Antarctica. States and districts with the largest representation are, in order, New York, Oregon, California, Washington, D.C., Texas, and Illinois. These numbers clearly show that hunger for engagement resources is not limited to coastal North American journalists, and is in fact global.

As shown in the chart below, users represent a wide variety of institutions. Gather seems to appeal to different kinds of journalists, including commercial, public, nonprofit and non-English language media, as well as journalism schools. Anecdotally, Project Team members have noticed that top level editors of global journalism networks such as the BBC are requesting invites alongside desk editors at small town newspapers. People from non-media organizations such as tech companies and nonprofits as well as independent freelancers and other kinds of consultants are also joining, showing that the issues addressed by Gather aren't limited to newsrooms. This demonstrates that engagement is an important issue for the communications field as a whole, not just journalism.

The second chart shows the types of engagement that members specialize in. Of note, 22% of Gather users focus primarily on comments and social media. We find this interesting, given that we generally consider these forms of engagement as more transactional than relational, due to the emphasis typically being on building audience and gauging readers' reaction to content, rather than on building two-way relationships with their audience. We are interested to learn whether being part of Gather helps transform newsrooms' uses of comment sections and social media to become more relational (and/or whether these users find support to branch out to more relational modes).

Currently, Gather is not collecting other demographic data on users, so other dimensions of diversity (e.g., race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status) are not yet captured.

Institution Types

Engagement Type/Specialties

What other results have we observed so far?

New adjunct activities that emerged as part of the intervention are starting to see results.

[Lightning Chats](#)

The [analytics data](#) show that, as of March 14, 2018, the 18 Lightning Chats hosted since May 2017 were attended by an average of 16.72 participants, including a mix of new and returning attendees. Of the total of 301 people who have attended, 45% were first-timers, while 55% have attended two or more times. The fact that first-time attendees makes up almost half of attendees aligns with the intention that Lightning Chats are interest-based conversations, given the topic-specific nature of individual sessions, while also providing enough actionable information to prompt return attendance. However, we will be watching over time to see whether more people return and whether some begin to attend regularly—two trends that indicate a more involved and enduring community of practice.

[Newsletter](#)

As of March 21, 2018, the Gather community Newsletter has 1,394 subscribers. Approximately 31% of subscribers open each newsletter. Of those, 5% are clicking through to the Gather platform itself. [According to MailChimp](#), the average open rate for newsletters is generally 15-28% depending on industry, and the average clickthrough rate is 2-5% depending on industry. This means that the community newsletter for Gather is operating at the top of or well above average, suggesting strong interest in the content and quality of the newsletters.

[Medium Site](#)

Our Medium publication, [Let's Gather](#), came out strong before and during the launch of the platform. It was an excellent opportunity to share and be transparent with our process and to build excitement about what we were doing. Before and around the time of launch, the publication attracted 56 visitors a day. The articles have averaged 975 views with 328 reads since the end of March.

Unfortunately, with our limited resources, we've been mostly focusing on ensuring that people continue to find value and connection on the Gather platform itself, leaving the Medium publication with little in the way of staffing hours or other resources. As a result, the publication has been dormant the majority of the time since the public launch of the Gather platform. However, in the coming months, we will be publishing a number of thought-provoking posts including a discussion regarding the research on and practice of engaged journalism: [Studying Emerging Engagement](#). DeVigal has been able to integrate Gather into his University of Oregon courses by encouraging students to pitch and write Medium posts, which has led to a more robust publication.

Next evaluation steps to document short-term outcomes

As we move forward, we are planning to observe how people use Gather, Lightning Chats, the Newsletter, and any other [adjunct activities](#), and how use changes over time. We'll be watching for trends in returning and regular participation in Lightning Chats to see if this adjunct activity builds community. The Gather team has created a framework for collecting, compiling, and analyzing data on how people use Gather on a monthly, weekly, daily, or real-time basis. This framework uses a number of tools, including analytics tools from Google, Medium, MailChimp, and FMYI.

Are members using *Gather* relationally and in alignment with the *Gather* mission?

We have a good starting place for understanding *who* is using Gather for what general purposes from the population-level analytics reported above. In-depth content analysis of user activity would give us deeper understanding of *how* and *why* people are using Gather. This information would help to distill the meaning and value of Gather's contribution to its CoP, how the CoP is developing over time, and how its members' own engagement practices might evolve to become increasingly relational.

We face two challenges in gathering that kind of data: platform functionality and resources.

While the Gather platform excels at compiling population-level information on Gather usage such as the analytics shown above, the platform does not yet allow a feasible way to understand what individual members are using the platform to do, making it difficult to assess how closely user activity aligns with Gather's mission. In-depth analysis tools that allow the Gather team to understand what individual members are using the platform to do are planned for a future release of the Gather platform.

Once these tools are implemented, the Gather team would like to perform an in-depth analysis of the content being produced and shared by users of the Gather platform. This analysis would look at a number of different usage categories, including how members are using the platform to find and connect with other members; find and share resources, information, mentorship, and support; converse and deliberate; generate and test new ideas; and collaborate with other members on mutual interests and projects.

This analysis would be supported by the population-level analytics data already provided by the

platform, as well as continued analysis of adjunct activities such as Lightning Chats and Newsletters using existing tools such as tracking sheets and surveys. But as is often the case with data collection, this kind of raw quantitative data doesn't necessarily offer the most important metrics, despite being easily measured and tracked over time.

In-depth content analysis, however, is time consuming and will likely require additional funding. At current funding levels, future analytics will be primarily limited to population-level data. With additional funding, the frequency and depth of any content analysis performed would increase, with the eventual goal of monthly comprehensive reports on how Gather members are using the platform and accompanying analyses of how that data can inform future evolution of the platform.

What parts of the civic communications ecosystem do *Gather* users represent?

Ongoing tracking and analysis of who is using Gather and what parts of the Gather core community they represent will utilize the existing analytics framework, as well as any analytics functionality added in the future, such as access to user content. In particular, the Google Forms sign-up form will be used to track the organizations, engagement levels, geographic locations, and job titles listed by invitation requesters, while the Gather platform's internal self-tagging category system will be used to track institutions and areas of expertise.

In the future, we hope to also collect other demographic data about users, so other dimensions of the community's diversity can be assessed.

Next evaluation steps to document long-term outcomes

Over time, we anticipate that supporting and growing the engagement journalism CoP will lead both to relational engagement becoming a transformational tool in existing media institutions, as well as to growth of new forms of high-quality media by people who are not currently identified as "journalists."

User surveys or interviews can help us find out how practices and organizational culture are changing (e.g., how newsrooms function, presence of community engagement editors, changes in job descriptions of engagement editors, changes in the way communities are covered, whose voices are heard and what issues are the focus), as well as how individual members of Gather are using the support, information, connections, adjunct activities (Lightning Chats and Newsletters) and resources they get through Gather to do things differently (for example, whether being part of Gather helps members branch out from focusing on the transactional modes of commenting and social media to more relational modes).

We'll also be eager to learn what kinds of interaction and engagement Gather is contributing to throughout communities, and how [Civic Communications Ecosystems](#) are impacted. We expect changes at multiple levels, including individual behavior changes; changes in organizational policies, practices and cultures; new ways for community members to engage in and with journalism.

One powerful way to understand outcomes of complex system change efforts at multiple levels is through [Outcome Harvesting](#). Outcome Harvesting is a "complexity aware" evaluation method to identify, verify, analyze and interpret outcomes of a program or initiative in contexts where relations of cause and effect are non-linear or not fully understood, or where multiple variables are not under the control of the program. As with the content analysis, these kinds of methods are very important,

but time consuming, and may require additional funding. Whether or not this method of evaluation will be utilized is dependent on securing the necessary resources, though we do consider it a long-term goal.

Evaluation Question 5: What's next?

Implications for how to support ongoing adaptive management are listed below, as are recommendations to others who might use a collaborative process to build a community of practice platform. Recommendations and next steps are addressed first in terms of the process used to build Gather, then in terms of its design.

Recommendations for reproducing (and improving on) our process

- Charters for committees and other project groups are helpful, but they should be designed to be adaptive; present and treat them as living documents. Whenever possible, be proactive in working through the process of document changes with affected groups, ideally before changes to the charter are implemented.
- Engage with tech partners early, preferably before forming auxiliary project groups. This allows for a better sense of which decisions are “team sport” decisions that can be reasonably made with project group input, and which decisions need be made executively by the core team and tech partners. However, err on the side of involving project groups when possible: a variety of perspectives on platform design and features will make for a more robust platform.
- Host an initial steering committee call to brief members on the process, and then reconvene them once design/tech is further along and ready for participation. Wait till there is a task list before starting regular Steering Committee meetings so that people feel that they are making a meaningful contribution.
- When forming a major project group, such as a steering committee, an establishing meeting should be held to clearly outline the group's purpose and ongoing involvement in the development process. Subsequent regularly scheduled meetings should not be held until the design process is ready for their participation. Additionally, a timeline and task list should be developed prior to holding regular group meetings in order to ensure that group members feel like they're making a meaningful contribution.
- Have expectations, processes, and communication protocols that allow for people's varying levels of involvement. Also recognize that some people may be able to be involved indefinitely while others will be able to commit for a shorter period, and structure groups accordingly. Finally, in order to encourage a greater diversity of viewpoints in project groups, consider offering small honorarium payments to some or all project group members to offset participation costs. Group members who work independently or for small organizations are especially good candidates.
- Wait to onboard non-working, purely advisory groups until there's something for them to do. If it's necessary to take advantage of momentum before that point, find alternative ways to connect with them, gauge their interest in the project, and keep them informed of any relevant progress.

Gather's next steps on process

- Re-form the Steering Committee, and nudge a few people off if they aren't able to continue to serve (at the time of this report, this process is in progress).
- Become more task-oriented with project groups. Give people specific assignments and deadlines as necessary. Adapt the Steering Committee charter to reflect the consultative and task-oriented nature of the group accordingly.
- Continue to explore the potential and role of the Advisory Committee (and other possible advisory groups) within the ongoing development of Gather.

Design lessons learned from Gather

- Design for a core group who are making active and meaningful contributions to the Gather platform (i.e., writing Medium posts, contributing case studies, participating in Slack conversations, etc); quality of involvement with the community of practice rather than quantity of involvement should be the focus.
- Given the diversity of definitions, techniques, and approaches to engagement, it's important to develop a clear set of values and a shared vocabulary around engagement that are used consistently within the context of the project.
- Hold relationship-building events and activities outside of the platform itself. These events and activities should be open, welcoming, fun, and should help build a sense of connection while supporting people being themselves. Even within the platform itself, events shouldn't just be focused on specific work around a topic, but also relationship building and connection.
- Make it easy for the community of practice to find and share news and success stories, as well as resources and tools that can be immediately useful to others within the community. Focus on concrete payoffs and solving problems that are coming up. Additionally, create multiple pathways for people to communicate what they need.
- Go where people already are. Integrate platform content into people's existing information flows, rather than leaving it there for people to find. Continue to give people fresh reasons to stop by, because just as in journalism, none of the work matters unless people can both find the content and find it useful.

Gather's next (and ongoing) steps in project design

- Periodically poll the community to assess how they feel about their interactions with Gather (Do they feel they're welcome? That they can be themselves? That their needs are being met? That they have a way to contribute? Etc.). Also use these polls to assess how beta users are searching for each other, and how they would like to search for each other in the future, and adjust user types accordingly.
- Continue to use monthly topics and other cohesion methods to provide content and community conversations with a guiding framework. These methods will also include the use of external tools, such as community newsletters and media aggregation tools for CoP content (e.g. Nuzzel).

- In addition to continuing to host Lightning Chats, develop a method to follow up with LC hosts to find out what they learned, what they did as a result, how it's going, as well as a method for people to suggest and host Lightning Chats in the first place. Additionally, develop a mechanism to continue Lightning Chat conversations after the Lightning Chat has concluded (open discussion Zoom sessions, Slack conversations, continued discussion on Gather itself, etc.).
- Increase the quantity, variety, and quality of content hosted on Gather prior to progressing from the public beta to the open beta or full release stage of development. Particular emphasis will be placed on content produced or suggested by the community, rather than content produced or found by the core team. Categories such as job and event listings, case studies, and resources are priorities.
- Continue to refine the platform's user interface based on community feedback. Work with our tech partner to integrate Gather with other services (such as Slack and Box) and make it more user-friendly.
- Provide a public viewing option that allows people to see some content on the platform and interact in a limited fashion without having to register. Essentially, allow those who are interested in learning more but who aren't ready to take the plunge to get a feel for what the platform is and can do for them.

Next steps with evaluation

- [For ongoing adaptation](#)
- [To document short-term outcomes](#)
- [To document long-term outcomes](#)

Appendix I

Adjunct Activities

[Lightning Chats](#)

(The link above will take you to the Gather page on [Lightning Chats](#), where you can read summaries of all the Chats, as well as see what Chats are coming up. You will need to be logged in to Gather to access it. Go [here](#) if you are not yet a member of Gather).

While working with the [Steering Committee](#) and [FMYI Partner](#) to develop Gather, Joy Mayer, the project's Community Manager, decided not to wait to offer activities to support the CoP. Coming out of [Elevate Engagement](#), fresh with the inspiration from the [Manifesto](#), Joy began offering weekly Lightning Chats.

Lightning Chats are brief, 30-40 minute video conferences hosted by Gather and facilitated by the Project Team. A member of the Gather community presents a project or question that they want feedback on, and other participants in the video conference ask questions and share their own thoughts and ideas. Lightning Chats happen once or twice a month on average, and are open to all members of Gather. Topics are selected ahead of time by the Gather team based on proposals from the community.

The Lightning Chats held to date have been:

- May 30, 2017 - Discussing money and engagement: Gather's first Lightning Chat addressed how engagement work connects to the financial health of our organizations.
- June 15, 2017 - Creating a community conversation guide for journalists: Andrew Rockway from The Jefferson Center led a conversation about the guide he's creating to help journalists host face-to-face conversations with community members.
- June 27, 2017 - How to scale conversations across divides: Eve Pearlman and Jeremy Hay from Spaceship Media led a conversation about their plans to launch a nationwide "dialogue journalism" experiment.
- July 12, 2017 - Engagement within news organizations: Ashley Alvarado (KPCC) and Jackie Hai (KJZZ) led a conversation about how to build support for engagement among colleagues and management.
- July 25, 2017 - Building a better engaged journalism toolkit: Fiona Morgan shared Free Press's [Engaged Journalism Toolkit](#) and received feedback on how to make it more accessible and useful for journalists.
- August 9, 2017 - Trust-building strategies: Joy Mayer discussed the early findings of the [Trusting News Project](#) and got feedback on some of trust-building strategies she's been developing for newsrooms.
- September 13, 2017 - Civic Communications Framework: Peggy Holman, Michelle Ferrier and [Journalism That Matters](#) hosted a chat on how journalism and communications ecosystems can support communities and democracy to thrive and build resilience. Take a look at their

[report](#) for background.

- September 26, 2017 - Engagement at the Texas Tribune: Alex Samuels, the Texas Tribune's new community reporter, talked about how the Tribune works to engage its statewide audience around government, policy and politics.
- October 11, 2017 - ONA lessons and insights: Participants shared engagement takeaways from the Online News Association conference and talked about what sessions they'd like to see.
- October 17, 2017 - Teaching engagement: How is engagement being taught to journalism students, and how SHOULD it be taught? Lori Shontz, Joy Mayer and other educators shared ideas and teaching materials from their work.
- October 24, 2017 - Facebook groups: How can journalists use Facebook groups to connect with their communities? When's the right time? How should people be invited? How do conversations get moderated? Angilee Shah of PRI and Hannah Wise of the Dallas Morning News led a great conversation tackling these questions and more.
- November 14, 2017 - Hiring for engagement: What should you look for in job candidates? What questions should you ask them? How is hiring for these jobs different from other journalism gigs? Terry Parris Jr. of ProPublica and Summer Fields of Hearken shared their insights.
- November 29, 2017 - Applying for engagement jobs: What story should you tell about yourself? What format should your portfolio take? What pitfalls should you avoid, especially when talking to hiring editors who don't specialize in engagement? Participants discussed insights gathered from Wired Magazine's Julia Bush, the Kansas City Star's Mary Kate Metivier, and WTHR Indianapolis' Sabrina Russello.
- December 14, 2017 - Hosting live events: Hosting live events. What purpose can they serve to bring people together in person? How much time do they take? What does everyone get out of them? And how do journalists learn how to moderate a conversation, organize food, market an event and handle other logistics? Hosted by Sarah Binder of Iowa Ideas, Megan Finnerty of USA TODAY, and jesikah maria ross of Capital Public Radio.
- January 18, 2018 - What tools help us in our engagement work? They can be outward facing (like ways to invite specific types of interactions) or internal (ways to organize communications, follow-up, etc.). Hosted by Ren LaForme of Poynter.
- February 8, 2018 - Bridging divides with face-to-face conversations: Participants discussed how journalists can convene conversations across divides in a way that enables real face-to-face connection and empathy. Hosted by Meredith Turk of Colorado Public Radio, Ross Reynolds of KUOW, and Andrew DeVigal of the Agora Journalism Center.
- February 22, 2018 - Bridging divides with online conversations: A lot of us do most of our engagement work online. Is there room there for building empathy and hosting meaningful interactions? Hosted by Eve Pearlman and Jeremy Hay of Spaceship Media, Peggy Holman of Journalism That Matters, and Halle Stockton of Public Source.
- March 14, 2018 - Membership programs: How can membership programs help news organizations build and reward loyalty? What can we do to celebrate and build relationships

with our most committed users? Hosted by the Membership Puzzle Project and The Atlantic.

- April 4, 2018 - Finding and filling local information needs: How do you find out what your community needs to know? How do you identify information gaps? And once you've found them, how does that knowledge play into what you decide to cover? Hosted by Ben DeJarnette of WhereBy.Us, Jesse Hardman of The Listening Post, and Mariko Chang of the Civil Beat.
- April 17, 2018 - Metrics tips and tricks: A chat about tools, strategies and workflows that help make sense of data and share its implications with our organizations. Hosted by Elizabeth Wolfe of the Chicago Tribune and Erica Smith of the Virginian Pilot.
- May 14, 2018 - Newsroom change: How can individual staff members create space for evolution, and for an expanded definition of journalism? How can we find allies for our engagement work? Hosted by Kristen Hare of Poynter, Julia Haslanger of Hearken, and Joy Mayer of Trusting News and Gather.

Medium site

The Gather Medium site was started quite early in the development phase as a way to keep the community updated before the platform existed. With the introduction of the Gather Community Newsletter, the Medium channel shifted in focus from development updates and the thought processes behind those updates to writings behind the activities and discussions on the platform. The Medium site provides platform updates, shares insights from the community, and hosts discussions about how Gather can best support engaged journalism's "community of practice." The site allows readers to share questions, suggestions make comments on the posts. Synopses of the Medium posts and links to them can be found [here](#).

Newsletter

The decision to create and launch Gather with a weekly newsletter was the result of recognizing that the platform wasn't intended to be a place that users and members will naturally gravitate to on a daily basis. In this early stage, it wasn't going to be a place that people will come back to unless there were specific pieces of information they were seeking. Producing a weekly newsletter will remind the community that they do have a resource that they can turn to when the time comes in their various project cycle. In addition, the popularity of newsletters has proven them as effective tools as it regularly lands in their email inbox.

Topic of the Month

Each month, the Gather team will focus on a specific topic. They will add or highlight case studies and resources and host Lightning Chats and other conversations related to the topic. Topics of the Month will be proposed directly by community members or identified in community conversations as areas of interest by the core team and steering committee.

Collaborative Leadership

Collaborative Teams & Roles

Project Team

Made up of paid staff and contractors, the Gather core Project Team is the primary management team for Gather. The team effectively acts as an executive committee for the project. Day-to-day management of the platform falls under their jurisdiction, including deciding on and implementing changes to the platform, the posting and curation of content, and collaboration with tech partners. The [team members](#) include a project executive director, project manager, project producer, community manager, and developmental evaluator.

Additionally, the team manages and facilitates the discussions and project work of the Steering and Advisory Committees. Although de facto final executive decision-making authority is held by the Project Team due to organic evolution of power structures over the course of the project, input from the Steering Committee forms the foundation of many team decisions. Similarly, the team solicits feedback on specific implementations of the project from the Advisory Committee, and incorporates this feedback into its decision-making process. This decision-making process is largely devolved and informal, with individual members of the team acting autonomously in their areas of expertise with input from their peers. Larger decisions are made through general team consensus.

Steering Committee

Made up of volunteer engagement professionals from a wide variety of backgrounds and experience, the Steering Committee is both a consultative and working group. Although the committee does not exercise executive authority, it is empowered by the Project Team and the Steering Committee Charter to make decisions regarding projects under its purview.

The Project Team brings key project components and objectives to the committee for consideration and discussion, and together the two groups set the agenda and general timeline for the development of Gather. The committee also works on specific core project-related tasks, such as the creation of development personas, content standards and structures for project content, and a unified project-wide taxonomic system. Large decisions, such as establishing project priorities and timelines, are voted on by all members, while committee members organize in task-based groups to work on smaller aspects of the project. These smaller groups are formed as needed, rather than operating under the umbrella of larger subcommittees.

Advisory Committee

In contrast to the Project Team and the Steering Committee, the Advisory Committee is a primarily passive listening group. The Community Manager keeps committee members apprised of the development status of the platform. Although largely dormant at this stage in the development of the project, in the future the Project Team will ask the committee to give feedback on new project developments. Additionally, specific members of the Advisory Committee will be asked to provide targeted feedback on individual project elements.

As with the Steering Committee, the Advisory Committee is made up of a wide variety of engagement professionals in order to represent as many stakeholder perspectives as possible. However, the number of Advisory Committee members is substantially greater than the number of Steering Committee members. Because the committee is not a working group, the specific credentials,

availability, and other limiting factors considered when selecting Steering Committee members do not apply, allowing for a wider net to be cast.

FMYI

FMYI is the primary tech partner in the Gather project, and is the vendor that provides the digital framework that Gather is built on. The FMYI team works closely with the Project Team to add new features, modify existing features, and otherwise implement changes to the Gather platform in order to meet the needs of the project. FMYI employees occasionally participate in Project Team and Steering Committee meetings. Additionally, they communicate with the Project Team between meetings via a private conversation thread on the Gather platform as well as online and face-to-face meetings.

Agora Journalism Center

The Agora Journalism Center at the School of Journalism and Communication (SOJC) is the University of Oregon's gathering place for innovation in communication and civic engagement. The center is also the primary partner in the Gather project; the original Knight grant for the project was issued to the institution, and the Agora Journalism Center serves as the project's institutional foundation. It is accordingly strongly represented in the Project Team, with two staff members serving as members of the team.

Journalism That Matters (JTM)

Journalism That Matters is a 501(c)(3) nonprofit dedicated to creating journalistic models that foster inclusive civic discourse and community engagement. JTM is also a regular contributor to and informal partner of the Gather project, having co-hosted two of the generative engagement conferences behind Gather, [Experience Engagement](#) and [Elevate Engagement](#). Additionally, the results of JTM research on civic communications and engagement journalism make up a significant portion of the theoretical foundation of the project.

Knight Foundation

The John S. and James L. Knight Foundation, or the Knight Foundation for short, is a national foundation dedicated to supporting journalism and the arts. Additionally, the foundation seeks to foster informed and engaged communities as essential parts of the democratic process. Along with the Democracy Fund, the Knight Foundation is the primary financial supporter of the Gather project.

Committee Charters

Steering Committee Charter

The Project Team wrote the Steering Committee Charter to serve as the committee's guiding document, akin to a set of bylaws. The charter designated the committee as project co-designers, along with the Project Team, and designated six broad categories as the primary responsibilities of the committee. These categories were content, community development, functionality/features, partnerships, funding, and managing internal vs. external (i.e. member vs. non-member) content viewing on the platform.

The charter also stipulated that there would be twelve voting members of the Steering Committee,

drawn from the engagement CoP, as well as five non-voting members drawn from FMYI and the Project Team serving in an ex officio capacity. Committee decisions were to be made by consensus, but when consensus could not be reached decisions would be made by majority vote, with ties being broken by the Project Team’s project executive director. The charter granted the committee the authority to make binding decisions on the categories listed above. The committee was also empowered by the charter to form standing subcommittees or temporary task forces as needed over time.

Advisory Committee Charter

As with the Steering Committee Charter, the Advisory Committee Charter serves as the committee’s guiding document. The charter designates the committee as an advisory board to both the Project Team and the Steering Committee, and charges committee members with offering feedback according to their expertise. Additionally, the charter assigns the Advisory Committee six broad categories as a primary focus, including content, community and network development, research and analysis, functionality/features, partnerships, and funding.

Unlike the Steering Committee, the Advisory Committee is not a working group. As a result, the charter serves as an organizational blueprint rather than effectively taking the place of bylaws, and does not include provisions for voting processes or the ability to form subcommittees. Advisory Committee members may be drawn from a much larger background than members of the Steering Committee, and do not necessarily need to come from the engagement CoP. Instead, committee members are selected for their ability to provide valuable feedback to the platform based on a variety of factors, including background, technical skill, and general expertise. There is no established limit on the number of committee members.

[Click here](#) for the onboarding process for the Steering and Advisory committees.

How did the collaborative process and the roles in the collaboration evolve?

	Original Fully Collaborative Model	Adapted Model
Project Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage the project • Manage the involvement of committees • Facilitate the collaborative participatory design process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Everything at left, plus: • Raise questions, bring ideas and questions to discuss, invite input, seek feedback • Make and implement decisions, using input from Steering Committee as much as possible • Inform Steering & Advisory committees, and growing community of interested future users, about decisions and progress • Work with tech partners to develop the platform • Add content to platform

		<i>(I.e., much of what was originally conceived as Steering Committee's role)</i>
Steering Committee as a Whole	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collectively make decisions about aspects of the platform, including content, functionality, user engagement, partnerships, funding and other issues Make decisions on proposals submitted by subcommittees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Give input, make recommendations and provide feedback to the Project Team to decide and implement No formal decision making; rather discussion and informal consensus, though there were a few informal votes, such as when the committee voted on the name <i>Gather</i>.
Sub-Committees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Made up of Steering & Advisory Committee members as well as other volunteers Develop proposals for the various aspects of the platform Work closely with Project Team to complete as yet undefined tasks related to the subcommittee's area of responsibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Made up of Steering Committee members only Task-oriented, rather than standing committees – take on specific tasks as needed by and with leadership by the Project Team (e.g., producing/ locating content or reviewing and giving feedback on content; reaching out to others who can help find/create content; conceptualizing structures and systems for sustaining some area of content or user engagement)
Advisory Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Give input on specific questions Volunteer for subcommittees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thus far, role has primarily been observing and being informed of progress Have not invited Advisory Committee members to join sub-committees

What drove the adaptation?

- Leadership and involvement needs change as the innovation progresses; the leadership model needs to adapt as the focus shifts from decisions and planning to task completion
- Volunteers seem to have less internal feeling that they have the authority to make decisions and have less time to understand the full context and complexity of every decision
- People who are paid have more time to devote and also seem to have a greater sense of decision-making authority
- Some decisions are more difficult to make democratically because of the time required and

the complexity. Decisions about processes, structure, protocols (e.g., onboarding process) are difficult to make democratically with a large group because they are complex, and have implications for power and control and involve design choices, not simply carrying out tasks such as populating a structure with content. These kinds of decisions take time, as they must allow for research, experimentation, deliberation, and discussion. Additionally, people who are volunteers may feel uncomfortable taking on this level of authority, and may find themselves wondering: “Who am I to decide on who should be allowed to do what?” Now that the structure is in place to help populate the project, however, shared ownership of tasks becomes easier.

- Meaningful yet flexible ways to be involved build sense of ownership, so it made sense to be adaptive
- Involvement is easier and can be more empowered in smaller, more task-oriented groupings
- Diversity of Steering Committee provided information, ideas, expertise and perspectives beyond what the Project Team has, and therefore improved decisions even if those decisions were ultimately made by the Project Team (they also took longer to make but were better). Decisions that were especially impacted by the diversity of the Steering Committee are the case study conceptualization, user interface design and development of the personas. For example, designing for key personas will make the platform useful to a broader constituency.
- Charter generated a sense of collective ownership and commitment even though the leadership structure and processes changed

What we learned about the conditions that support ongoing development of the innovation

- Careful selection of Project Team members for skills in project management, design, development, communications, community management and engagement, and evaluation
- Paid Project Team that does most of the “hands-on” development work
- Community manager whose job it is to be excited when someone joins and to facilitate their onboarding and support their involvement
- Carefully curated Steering Committee made up of people who are at the forefront of the engagement field and who have a diversity of talents and perspectives and who represent
- Starting with a Charter that sets original intention to have shared decision making and that clarifies purpose and process, but is also adaptive to respond to stages of development of the team and the project
- Flexible expectations for committee involvement that allow everyone to stay involved at their level of availability

What we learned about the conditions that need to be considered in managing collaborative process.

- The role of the Steering Committee and therefore the charter will evolve as the work that needs to be done changes and as the group matures
- Tech development is slower than planned
- Varied participation levels – volunteer committee members will participate at different levels,

and individuals' involvement may change over time as their other obligations take up bandwidth

- Committee structure has a necessary inefficiency of getting and giving feedback, developing ideas, getting work done, especially when people are volunteering and decisions require input, multiple perspectives and deliberation
- Though there are people who want to contribute, there may not be much for them to do early on, so don't expect to have ways for them to be very involved at the beginning

Leadership Models

Adapted from Tannenbaum & Schmidt; Crosby

Priorities of the Project Team and Steering Committee

Project Team

The Project Team has focused primarily on building out the committees, developing Gather membership and content production screening and selection methods, and selectively promoting the platform through [Medium posts](#) and targeted e-mail communications. Getting the Gather platform itself ready for public launch has also been a high priority, with the Project Team working with the Steering Committee to collect, edit, appropriately categorize, and publish initial platform content. As the adjunct activities came into being, producing [Lightning Chats](#), the [Newsletter](#), writing or commissioning [Medium](#) articles and curating the [Topic of the Month](#) have also become part of content production.

In addition to its own project goals, the Project Team has emphasized ongoing collaboration and discussion with the Steering Committee, as well as the facilitation of committee meetings. Implementation of Steering Committee projects, such as a unified platform-wide taxonomic system, have been incorporated into Project Team platform development. Consultation with committee member task groups remains an ongoing priority for the Project Team.

A final priority for the Project Team is project analysis and improvement via the development evaluation. Data on platform usage as well as the effect of the platform on the CoP are tracked through each stage of development, and informs both required funding-related project documentation and ongoing development of the platform itself. Additionally, this data is being used to track and inform adjustments to project organization and management.

Steering Committee

Steering Committee priorities have varied throughout the development process of the platform. Early priorities have included developing naming conventions and general nomenclature for the platform – including the name Gather itself – as well as the creation of development personas to be used while building out the platform. These priorities were identified in collaboration with the Project Team via a survey of committee members. Later priorities include continued development of categorical and taxonomic systems for the project, the curation of initial research listings and other engagement resources, and encouraging CoP members to interact with the platform. Future priorities will be assessed by the committee soon after the platform launches publicly, which will mark a transition into the second phase of the project. As with previous priorities, the Steering Committee will select elements to prioritize in the second phase through collaboration with the Project Team.

Past and present priorities have largely conformed to the six categories of focus outlined the Steering Committee charter, though only some of the categories have seen committee activity. Specifically, the committee has worked on projects falling within the content, community development, functionality/features, and partnerships categories. Meanwhile, committee work on projects within the funding and managing internal vs. external content categories has been minimal or non-existent. This is primarily due to the shift in the executive decision-making process. With the Project Team holding final executive authority, decisions regarding funding and public access to the project are by necessity handled by that team rather than by the Steering Committee.

Process for Committee Onboarding

Steering Committee

Steering Committee candidates were selected by the project executive director in two steps. The director first sent a mass email to the CoP with an attached volunteer form and those respondents who indicated they had time and interest to serve on the committee were added to the list of potential candidates. The director also did targeted personalized invitations and follow up phone conversations with specific individuals he felt were ideal candidates for the committee on account of background, experience, and other qualifications. The goal was to get diverse perspectives from those working in newsrooms, classrooms and other arenas, with a background in journalism, engagement, technology, and experience design. These individuals were also added to the list of potential candidates.

The Project Team considered potential candidates according to a rubric of candidate interest, availability, and skills, perspectives, or backgrounds relevant to the project. Candidates deemed a good fit for the committee were then sent an invitation to join. This invitation was sent by the community manager. The invitation included a basic summary of the responsibilities of the Steering Committee, a list of tasks in need of doing, upcoming meeting times and dates, and a copy of the Steering Committee Charter. If the candidate accepted, they became a member of the Steering Committee.

Although this process has been implemented in two rounds of Steering Committee recruitment, a different process may evolve during the next phase. Future Steering Committee candidates may be selected through different means as the needs of the project evolve.

In our selection process for our second set of Steering Committee members, we sought out different expertise and perspective. Whereas the first set tended to include people with specific skills in product development (user experience, interface design, product development), the second group of people had a keen interest in sustaining a high level of engagement to keep the community of practice together.

Advisory Committee

The onboarding process for the Advisory Committee mirrors that of the Steering Committee. As with the Steering Committee, candidates were selected through a combination of volunteer form responses and targeted outreach to specific individuals.

The community manager sent invitations to those who indicate an interest in serving on the Advisory Committee. The invitation included a basic summary of the responsibilities of the Advisory Committee, a list of project elements that most need feedback, and a copy of the Steering Committee Charter. If the candidate accepted, they became a member of the Advisory Committee.

Team members

Project Team Members

- [Andrew DeVigal](#): Project Executive Director
- [Keegan Clements-Housser](#): Project Manager & Producer
- [Joy Mayer](#): Community Manager

- [Yve Susskind](#): Developmental Evaluator
- [Ben DeJarnette](#): Project Manager (former)

Steering Committee Members

First set

- Andrew Haeg, GroundSource
- Ashley Alvarado, KPCC
- Carrie Watters, Arizona Republic
- Chris Faraone, BINJ
- Jake Batsell, Southern Methodist University
- Jeanne Brooks, Virago Futures
- Michelle Ferrier, Ohio University
- Niala Boodhoo, Illinois Public Media
- Pamela Behrsin, CALmatters
- Peggy Holman, Journalism That Matters
- Rodney Gibbs, Texas Tribune
- Simon Nyi, Illinois Humanities
- Subramaniam Vincent, The Trust Project

Second set

- Alexandra Smith, WhereBy.Us
- Andrew Rockway, Jefferson Center
- Ashley Alvarado, KPCC
- Ben DeJarnette, BridgeLiner
- Benjamin Rose, Christian Science Monitor
- Carrie Brown, CUNY Graduate School of Journalism
- Emily Olson, NPR
- Gracie McKenzie, CityLab
- Julia Haslanger, Hearken
- Lauren Katz, Vox
- Lori Shontz, UO School of Journalism and Communication
- Peggy Holman, Journalism That Matters
- Simon Nyi, Illinois Humanities
- Yve Susskind, Praxis Associates LLC

Advisory Committee Members

- Joe Amditis, Center for Cooperative Media
- Craig Anderson, Center for Innovation and Sustainability in Local Media at UNC School of Media and Journalism
- Kyle Bozentko, Jefferson Center

- Burgess Brown, New School
- Carrie Brown, CUNY
- Jessica Clark, Dot Connector Studio
- Sue Cross, Institute for Nonprofit News
- Molly de Aguiar, Dodge
- Brandon Echter, Science Friday
- Mike Fancher, Agora Journalism Center
- Jon Funabiki, Renaissance Journalism
- Daniela Gerson, Cal State, Northridge
- Cole Goins, Reveal from The Center for Investigative Reporting
- Teresa Gorman, Democracy Fund
- Anika Gupta, National Geographic
- Sam Guzik, Newsday
- Jesse Hardman, Listening Post
- Olivia Henry, KALW Public Radio
- Julia Haslanger, Hearken
- Madison Kahn, Self (formerly of Medium)
- Kate Lesniak, Bitch Media
- Andrew Losowsky, Coral Project
- Fiona Morgan, Free Press
- Meghan Murphy, ONA
- Anna Nagle, Nature
- Terry Parris, Jr, ProPublica
- Damian Radcliffe, University of Oregon
- Greg Retsinas, KGW-TV, KGW.com, Portland, Ore.
- Andrew Rockway, Jefferson Center
- Usha Rodrigues, Deakin University
- Lori Shontz, University of Oregon
- Emily Singer, Gear Patrol (gearpatrol.com)
- Michael Skoler, Louisville Public Media
- Josh Stearns, Democracy Fund
- Kim, Walsh-Childers, University of Florida
- Paul Waters, Democracy Fund
- Amanda Zamora, Texas Tribune

Community of Practice

What is a Community of Practice (CoP)?

A community of practice is a group of individuals and organizations that interact with each other regularly over a shared cause, purpose, or goal. Communities of practice differ from communities of interest in that they go beyond simple shared interests and are specifically made up of practitioners operating within the area of focus. Members of the community develop and share formal or informal repositories of actionable knowledge related to the area of practice with one another, including working methods, tools, solutions to problems and best practices. Further development of these repositories happens through shared experiences.

Gather seeks to support the development of the engagement journalism community of practice. It

does this through providing a living repository of actionable knowledge related to the field and a venue for people to connect and share ideas and support and collaborate on engagement projects. Content and conversation hosted on Gather is by and for members of the community of practice, and is developed through community interaction and discussion.

“Communities of practice are groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly...A community of practice is not merely a community of interest—people who like certain kinds of movies, for instance. Members of a community of practice are practitioners. They develop a shared repertoire of resources: experiences, stories, tools, ways of addressing recurring problems—in short a shared practice.” ([Wenger-Trayner](#))

What is Gather’s CoP?

Gather’s core community is the engagement journalism CoP. For the purposes of this report, that community is defined as journalists, educators and students, community advocates, and other communications practitioners who are developing and implementing new strategies for ensuring that media are with, by, for and as the public. Within the context of Gather, engaged journalists and journalism educators in particular are the primary focus of this community. However, this focus does not exclude non-journalistic media practitioners or other media stakeholders, such as community advocates.

This definition draws from existing models and engagement communities, such as those articulated by [Journalism That Matters](#) and other similar organizations, as well as neighborhood associations and other community [Experience](#) and [Elevate Engagement](#) conferences, and their resulting [Manifesto](#), further clarified this definition by broadening the scope of who is directly involved in engaged journalism. Journalists are only one part of the equation, and in order for true engaged journalism to thrive, community connectors, organizers, and engagers must be involved as well. The Experience and Elevate Engagement conferences were designed with this concept in mind, and invited the aforementioned non-journalistic stakeholders to attend and participate. The manifesto and [JTM Engagement Framework](#) that came out of the conference galvanized Gather’s core community.

Developmental Evaluation

[Developmental Evaluation](#) is a method-neutral approach to tracking and analyzing a new system, project or process. Unlike more traditional evaluation paradigms that rely on a formative or summative approach, Developmental Evaluation (DE) is part of the process of incubating and building an innovation. DE remains ongoing throughout part or all of the development of the innovation, and projects that are always responding to changes in their environment and therefore always innovating may use DE continuously. Data uncovered during the evaluation are analyzed and then fed back into the development of the innovation. Thus, both the development process and the evaluation process change organically and interactively. The *Gather* project uses DE as a core part of its development process, meaning that how members use and interact with *Gather* will directly affect how *Gather* develops going forward.

Engagement

In the context of media organizations, engagement refers to the process of ensuring that media organizations are responsive to their audiences and communities and vice versa. Though engagement can be either [relational](#) or [transactional](#) in nature, engagement fundamentally involves a two-way exchange of information between the two parties. This forms a recursive process, through which media organizations produce content increasingly influenced by and in line with audience or community needs and desires.

“Engagement happens when members of the public are responsive to newsrooms, and newsrooms are in turn responsive to members of the public.” ([Hearken](#))

“Engagement is about reaching out to your community, joining and hosting conversations, and inviting your community to be collaborators in journalism by sharing their curiosities, experiences and expertise.” ([Joy Mayer](#))

Transactional engagement

Traditionally, journalistic engagement has been presented as fairly transactional. That is to say, “the value proposition of engagement is mostly one-way.” Engagement techniques and methods are used to bolster the sales, subscribers, and reputation of journalists, rather than considering what the public gets out of the interaction. An example is the the Association for Education in Journalism and Mass Communication’s (AEJMC) News Engagement Day. During this day, the AEJMC encourages the public to engage with news and “promote understanding of the principles and processes of journalism in a democratic society.” It’s clear what journalists get out of this exchange but less clear what’s in it for the public.

Transactional engagement can be perfectly acceptable. It’s even sometimes necessary; when used with clarity and transparency, transactional engagement methods can be used to educate the public about a journalistic organization’s values and mission.

Relational Engagement

Engagement doesn’t start and end with the transactional form. It can also be relational – the notion that journalists should not only look at what they get out of engagement, but what the community gets out of it as well. Beyond just representing a more even value proposition, relational engagement also suggests that the community should be equal partners, collaborators, and even contributors to journalism. Journalists can learn a lot from their communities, and communities can learn a lot from their journalists. Engagement can and should go both ways (for more on this theme, see [The Continuum of Engagement](#)).

Relational engagement refers to a method of engagement that focuses on building long-term collaborative relationships and trust between journalists and communities. “When authentic interactions happen, they encourage reciprocity, which sparks a virtuous cycle that cultivates trust.” Interactions became relational rather than extractive. Instead of treating communities as audiences passively consuming media, relational engagement focuses on involving communities as “active, engaged and powerful community agents. Increasingly trustworthy relationships improve the capacity to see and engage power dynamics... Local stakeholders, including journalists,

politicians, residents, nonprofit organizations and other community agents with different roles and areas of expertise, work together to answer questions. Solutions emerge from a conversation where maintaining trust, transparency and accountability are paramount” ([JTM Engagement Framework](#)). In relational engagement, community members not only become active participants and consumers of community media, but also engaged and empowered agents of their community.

In Gather, this manifests in two ways. First, Gather is intended to support this method of engagement within its CoP to both provide information to the CoP and empower the CoP to collaborate, produce, and share information of their own. Second, the content that is collected, shared and amplified via Gather supports newsrooms, media and community organizations and individual agents of change to practice relational engagement within their communities.

Engagement can be placed on a spectrum from transactional to relational with the public’s activities ranging from learning, following, endorsing (transactional) to participating, collaborating, and leading (relational).

Gather

[Gather](#) is a project + platform to support community-minded journalists and other engagement professionals. Learn more about Gather [here](#), and [request an invite](#) to participate in the community.

JTM’s Engagement Framework

Since 2015, [Journalism That Matters](#) has been working with a [developmental evaluator](#) to develop and begin to test a framework to understand the relationship between community engagement and journalism. The framework is based on analysis of qualitative data generated in two convenings, co-hosted by the [Agora Journalism Center](#) and JTM ([Experience Engagement in 2015](#), and [Elevate Engagement in 2017](#)).

In the time between the two gatherings, the Developmental Evaluation team collaborated with two journalism-related community engagement projects and followed the work of a few others to learn how the [principles articulated in 2015](#) operate at the local level and how they can inform and support new, emerging engagement efforts.

In late 2016, the JTM Developmental Evaluation team published a [Framework](#) laying out its deepened understanding of the principles, as well as what they’d learned about the roles, activities, values, assumptions, and challenges of the emerging local communications systems.

The Framework was a touchstone during [Elevate Engagement in 2017](#), which generated a [Manifesto](#) calling for the creation of a CoP to support journalists working in alignment with the [Framework](#)’s principles. In brief, those principles are:

- Nothing about us without us
- Speak truth to empower
- Listening is our superpower.

Outcomes in detail: Intended short-term outcomes

1. Members of the CoP will use *Gather* in alignment with the *Gather* [mission](#), to:

- Find each other
- Find and share resources and information
- Find and share support and mentorship
- Converse and deliberate
- Generate and test out new ideas
- Collaborate

2. Activity in *Gather* will be relational (or will become more so) with substantial representation of activities such as:

- Sharing of content
- Posting and answering questions
- Initiating and participating in conversations on topics of their interest
- Participating in Lighting Chats
- Suggesting and hosting Lighting Chats
- Connecting with each other to directly share, mentor, learn together
- Connecting with each other to collaborate on projects
- Continuing relationships that were initiated face-to-face (and vice versa)
- Sharing stories of what they are doing, how their collaborations are going and what they are learning (this may happen in the companion [Medium](#) site or [Newsletter](#))
- Inviting others to join
- Initiating and leading in other ways

3. Over time, *Gather* users will represent diverse parts of the [civic communications ecosystem](#).

For example, users would represent a variety of:

- Institution types such as:
 - Commercial Media
 - Public Media
 - Nonprofit Media
 - Nonprofit Organization
 - University
 - Tech Company
 - Non-English Language Media
 - Freelance
 - Consulting
- Engagement types, such as:

- Crowdsourcing
 - Crowdfunding
 - Facilitated Dialogue
 - Public-Powered Reporting
 - Live Events
 - Diversity, Equity & Inclusion
 - Comments
 - Social Media
 - Collaborative Reporting
 - User-Generated Content
 - Apps & Interactives
 - Research, Evaluation & Teaching
 - Niche Audiences
 - Open Reporting
- Jobs or roles, such as:
 - Hiring editor
 - Aspiring engager
 - Experienced engager
 - Marketing manager / accidental engager
 - Student engager
 - Academic
 - Reporter/traditional journalist
 - Ethnic or community-based journalist
 - Beat reporter
 - Policy maker
 - Issue stakeholder
 - Solutions journalist
 - [Community weaver](#)
 - [Guardian\(s\)/Steward\(s\)](#)
 - [Coach](#)
 - [Allies/Partners](#)

They will also represent demographic and geographic diversity.

What is a Theory of Change?

- A theory of change (ToC) describes the process and reasons why a desired change can be expected to happen. ToCs explain and map the relationship between what a project or innovation does and how these activities lead or contribute to achievement of desired goals. When something new is being created, its ToC informs the design of the innovation and points to what is important to evaluate.
- A ToC begins by considering the present situation (the problem) and identifying the desired long-term impact, and then fills in the causal relationships between the two. These steps between the present and long-term impact include the intervention theorized will lead to short- and long-term outcomes.
- TOCs also articulate the key assumptions underlying our present thinking about the parts of

the theory and how they interact.

- TOCs are not static. As implementation of the innovation proceeds, the evaluation process helps deepen understanding to refine and articulate relationships within the ToC. ToCs become more complex and elaborate as we discover mechanisms that explain why one thing leads to another, as well as conditions that either support the development of the innovation and its success, or that are “facts of life” and need to be taken into consideration.
- An evaluation that uses ToC as its basis will report on the results and value of the intervention, and also on what has been learned about the ToC itself.

“With,” “by,” but also “as”

Thanks to Kate McKegg and Nan Wehipeihana for sharing the groundbreaking insight that participation as a cultural group is different from participation with or even by them. Working in New Zealand as evaluators in Maori communities, Kate and Nan have been developing the concept of “as Maori,” which “recognizes the desire of Maori to have control over their future direction as well as the strong motivation for Maori to determine the solutions that work for them. Furthermore, it affirms the validity and legitimacy of Maori knowledge and ways of doing things, of the need for space for Maori to live and participate in New Zealand as Maori.” (Patton, M.Q. (2011) *Developmental Evaluation*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press. Page 276.)

Appendix II:

[Medium](#) Synopses

The Future of Journalism is Already Here

Ben DeJarnette | February 21, 2017 ([link](#))

Engagement journalism, specifically relational engagement journalism, is already present in the industry. It's just not evenly spread out yet. Gather is intended to be a tool to help bring the engagement community of practice together for the purposes of collaborating, sharing ideas, and spreading best practices. The Gather project is still in its infancy, but there's already a strong team working on it, and this Medium post shows you who they are. Watch this Medium channel for more info (and to find ways to get involved).

How Do You Support a Community of Practice?

Ben DeJarnette | March 1, 2017 ([link](#))

Community trust in journalism is broken, and engaged journalists are the technicians that can fix it. It all starts with a community of practice, however. Solutions to the problems facing the industry won't come from some top-down model or manual; instead, they'll come from practitioners sharing what is and isn't working for them. That's where Gather comes in. The platform is being designed with busy journalists in mind, and will also accommodate varying levels of experience (and different types) of engagement. The platform is intended to be both more flexible and fluid than a Facebook group, but also more focused. The most useful resource available in engagement journalism is the expertise of other engagement journalists, so helping the community of practice communicate with each other is fundamental to Gather.

Are You an Engaged Journalist?

Joy Mayer | March 9, 2017 ([link](#))

Gather is for the engaged journalism community, but how do you know if you're an engaged journalist? Engagement work can be found in a variety of media organizations and can be found in a plethora of media roles. Listing them all isn't feasible. However, this post does list nine example reasons someone might be a good fit for *Gather*. These examples are:

- Maybe you're realizing there are segments of your community that you're not reaching or hearing from the way you'd like.
- Maybe you're wondering if it's possible to build bridges across the political divide.
- Maybe you're looking for new ways to invite and tell the stories of your community.

- Maybe you're a reporter hoping to base your work on what your community most needs to know.
- Maybe you run a community newspaper that has been doing good old-fashioned engagement work for decades, but now you want to update your approaches.
- Maybe you're in a large organization that can be slow to evolve, but you believe in being more transparent about your work.
- Maybe you work in social media and are wondering how to more consistently move beyond counting likes and shares to instead focus on longer-term relationships.
- Maybe your organization is looking for ways to build connections in your community, not just share information.
- Maybe you're a teacher who wants to be including community engagement in your journalism classes, but you're not sure what that would look like.

Front Porch Forum, Gather, and the Power of Intranet

Ben DeJarnette | March 29, 2017 ([link](#))

The Front Porch Forum, which started as a community-produced neighborhood newsletter in 2000 and grew to become community intranet serving almost 200 Vermont communities today, is a perfect example of community engagement in action. Rather than chasing profit, shares, or clicks, the Front Porch Forum grew to its current impressive place in the market by instead focusing on supporting conversation, candor, and community among neighbors. *Gather* aims to do something very similar, but with a community of practice rather than a neighborhood. In particular, *Gather* aims to incorporate many of the best elements of an intranet, which is why FMYI – a tech company that designs intranets – is *Gather*'s primary tech partner. Intranets can be used to drive engagement beyond just *Gather* and neighborhood forums, too; political action networks, digital “town halls” or public squares, and local news can all be done via intranet.

Learning ‘Engagement’ Can Be a Lonely Quest. It Doesn’t Have to Be.

Joy Mayer | April 18, 2017 ([link](#))

With engagement journalism still an emergent field, at least in its current incarnation, practitioners often practice alone. Many newsrooms only have one or two people assigned to managing engagement efforts for the entire outlet. While the term “engagement” is becoming more widespread throughout the industry, the meaning of the term – and the tools and best practices associated with it – varies from place to place from practitioner to practitioner. Newsrooms stumble over the same challenges, but because they operate in isolation from one another, lessons learned don’t spread, and the proverbial wheel is constantly reinvented.

Gather aims to help solve this problem by creating a place where practitioners can connect and share ideas, brainstorm new projects, or just find support in general. As a way to get a better sense of how we can best support our community of practice, asked members of our steering committee what they were hoping to see on *Gather*. Their responses included developing common terminology and best practices, the creation and implementation of new engagement practices and techniques, collaboration within the community, and better teaching techniques.

Elevate Engagement Manifesto

Joy Mayer | July 17, 2017 ([link](#))

The [Elevate Engagement](#) conference, which was co-hosted by the Agora Journalism Center and Journalism That Matters, was a convening of the type of community of practice that *Gather* hopes to support. 130 journalists, researchers, engagement practitioners, and community leaders made an appearance, representing multiple industries, countries, and even continents. This Medium posts represents the efforts of Joy Mayer, Kyle Bozentko, and March Twisdale to record and distill key take-away ideas from the conference into a manifesto. In addition to general findings, the manifesto identified three core principles for the engagement community of practice to consider moving forward:

- We belong to a community of remote colleagues, and we crave connections.
- Our values and goals unite us.
- We need to learn from one another.

Implementation of these core principles will vary from group to group, person to person, but there are a few ways we can do this. Collaborate with one another on specific projects. Join community discussion and collaboration groups, like the [Experience Engagement Facebook Group](#) and *Gather*. Help one another find and land jobs and other connections within the industry. Track what the community of practice is doing, and share the results. Most of all, work together, not apart.

Get Ready to ‘Gather’

Ben DeJarnette | July 20, 2017 ([link](#))

“*Gather* is a collection of searchable resources. It’s a place to learn (and borrow) from existing projects. It’s a hub for collaboration. It’s an advanced how-to guide for engagement vets and an on-ramp for newbies. It’s a digital meeting space where engaged journalism’s budding community of practice can continue to grow and evolve.” That was the original vision behind *Gather* when it was conceived of. Now that the *Gather* closed beta is about to launch, thanks in no small part to the hard work of FMYI and the steering committee, this post takes a look at how that vision has translated into practical reality so far.

It’s not all there yet, but it will be. *Gather* will continue to evolve and grow as it gets closer to a full public release (and beyond). The release schedule is based on priorities identified by *Gather* staff and the steering committee, with features deemed more essential making earlier appearances. Currently, *Gather* has a variety of resources, case studies, job listings, discussion spaces open to members, and video “Lightning Chats,” where engagement practitioners can get together to discuss a common challenge or brainstorm ideas around a specific project. Features yet to be implemented include (in order of predicted appearance) a pair of newsletters, a more intuitive user profile system, topics of the month, and new ways to collect community input. Additionally, once *Gather* is closer to a full public launch, non-members will be given a way to see *Gather* content in order to avoid becoming a walled garden.

Practicing What We Preach

Lori Shontz | August 10, 2017 ([link](#))

A healthy community of practice for engaged journalism can’t just start and end with professional practitioners. Journalism students – and the instructors who teach them – need to be part of the process as well. Best practices are often instilled in the classroom, and it’s difficult to instill the best practices of engaged journalism when it’s largely absent from the existing curriculum. What does involving students and instructors look like? University of Oregon School of Journalism and

Communication professor Lori Shontz, an attendee of [Elevate Engagement](#), has some thoughts.

In her experience, she writes, students have raised issue with the “traditional” way they’re taught to cover civics. They point out that they’re taught to go cover city hall as gatekeepers, rather than spending time with the community, finding out what political issues matter to them, and then bringing their community’s concerns to city hall. Similarly, the notion of journalism serving the democratic process is often invoked, but rarely explained. How does journalism serve the democratic process? How *should* it serve the democratic process? The industry is rapidly changing, and so curriculum needs to keep up. Humility is key, especially when the traditional media model has been turned on its head, so it behooves instructors and practitioners alike to listen to journalism students.

Elevating Engagement Through Design

Chelsea Anne Brown | August 23, 2017 ([link](#))

As traditional roles and methods used by the journalism industry continue to change along with the media landscape at large, the way journalists present news – and the way readers interact with news – needs to change as well. This goes beyond simply presenting news in a traditional format but with a different perspective on journalistic objectivity and with community input, although these too are important. Rather, it encompasses the very format and interactivity of presented news itself.

In practical terms, this means that journalistic content needs to adapt and grow into how we use and interact with media today. Instead of static content, today’s journalism needs to react and respond to the specific needs of individual members of the public. Content needs to be able to be shared quickly and easily, with key quotes, datapoints, or other takeaways designed to be sent to others or shared. Content also needs to be truly interactive, form inviting public conversation throughout published content to actively seeking out differing or unheard viewpoints during the content creation process. Finally, journalists need to embrace experimentation, even if that sometimes means failure; in the digital age, success doesn’t hinge on getting something tried and tested to print.

It’s time to *Gather*, and we hope you’ll join us

Joy Mayer | October 1, 2017 ([link](#))

Gather is transitioning from a closed beta to a public beta, and everyone’s invited to come take a look and give feedback. While invitations are still required, anyone can request one, and very few people will be turned away. Most of the features listed in the [closed beta announcement](#) have been implemented, and only a few major features remain, including giving non-members read access to the platform. While additional news information about *Gather* will continue to be posted in the [Experience Engagement Facebook Group](#), and *Gather* is not intended to be a replacement for existing platforms and tools. However, with the public beta rolling out, more and more information will be posted on the *Gather* platform itself.

The Continuum of Engagement

Andrew DeVigal | October 3, 2017 ([link](#))

Traditionally, journalistic engagement has been presented as fairly transactional. That is to say, “the value proposition of engagement is mostly one-way.” Engagement techniques and methods are used to bolster the sales, subscribers, and reputation of journalists, rather than considering what the public gets out of the interaction. A perfect example of this is the News Engagement Day put on by the

Association for Education in Journalism and Mass Communication (AEJMC). During this day, the AEJMC encourages the public to engage with news and “promote understanding of the principles and processes of journalism in a democratic society.” It’s clear what journalists get out of this exchange. Less clear is what’s in it for the public.

Transactional engagement is perfectly acceptable. It’s even sometimes necessary; when used with clarity and transparency, transactional engagement methods can be used to educate the public about a journalistic organization’s values and mission. However, engagement doesn’t start and end there. It can also be relational – the notion that journalists should not only look at what they get out of engagement, but what the community gets out of it as well. Beyond just representing a more even value proposition, relational engagement also suggests that the community should be equal partners, collaborators, and sometimes contributors to journalism. Journalists can learn a lot from their communities, and communities can learn a lot from their journalists. Engagement can and should go both ways.